

**“FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF CLARITHROMYCIN
FLOATING TABLET”**

**DISSERTATION
SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULLFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE DEGREE IN
BACHELOR OF PHARMACY (B.PHARM)**

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ABSTRACT

Clarithromycin is a macrolide antibiotic that is commonly used for the treatment of various bacterial infections, including respiratory tract infections, skin and soft tissue infections, and *Helicobacter pylori* infections. It is practically insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, but soluble in acetone and methylene chloride. It is a semisynthetic macrolide antibiotic that binds to the P site of susceptible organisms reversibly and may inhibit bacterial protein synthesis that blocks amino acyl translocation and formation of initiation complex. Thus, microbial protein synthesis is inhibited. Therefore, the high concentration of clarithromycin in the stomach is essential to ensure effective eradication of *H. pylori* irrespective of its rapid absorption through the gastrointestinal tract. Despite its effectiveness, the bioavailability of clarithromycin can be limited due to poor solubility. Hence, floating drug delivery system is proposed to enhance bioavailability and improve gastric residence time.

In the present study, an attempt was made to design and optimize, by literature review, floating matrix tablets of Clarithromycin using HPMC K15M and ethyl cellulose as polymers and citric acid and sodium bicarbonate as gas forming agents by using the direct compression technique. The formulated tablets were evaluated for post and precompression studies. All the formulations showed a floating time greater than 24 hours.

ABBREVIATIONS

API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
AUC	Area Under the Curve
FDDS	Floating Drug Delivery System
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy
GRFDDS	Gastro retentive Floating Drug Delivery System
HPMC	Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose
RPM	Revolution per minute

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 ORAL CONTROLLED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Oral drug delivery (ODD) is the most preferred and convenient route of drug administration due to high patient compliance, cost-effectiveness, least sterility constraints, flexibility in the design of dosage form and ease of production. However, some of the drugs administered orally face several physical, biological, and biochemical barriers which lower the therapeutic efficacy of the drugs before getting absorbed into the systemic circulation. (Deviprasad Sahoo, 2021)

Controlled drug delivery system (CDDS)

Controlled drug delivery systems are capable of controlling the rate of drug delivery, sustaining the duration of therapeutic activity and/or targeting the delivery of drug to a tissue. A controlled drug delivery system delivers the drug at a particular rate, maintains safe and effective blood levels for a period as long as the system continues to deliver the drug. Controlled drug delivery shows constant blood levels of the active ingredient as compared to the uncontrolled fluctuations observed when multiple doses of immediate releasing conventional dosage forms are administered.

Advantages of CDDS (Jeganath. S, 2018)

- Increased patient compliance
- Reduction on dosing frequency
- Avoidance of night time dosing
- Reduced fluctuations in circulatory drug levels
- More uniform effect
- Decreased side effects like reduced GI irritation
- Delivery of drug in the vicinity of site of action
- More efficient utilization of active agent
- Reduction in health care cost through improved therapy

Disadvantages of CDDS (Jeganath. S, 2018)

- Poor in vitro – in vivo correlation
- Toxicity due to dose dumping
- High cost
- Reduced potential for dosage adjustments
- Poor systemic availability in general
- Stability problem

1.2 GASTRO RETENTIVE DOSAGE FORM (GRDF)

Gastroretentive dosage forms are drug delivery systems which remain in the stomach for extended period of time. Their application can be advantageous in the case of drugs that are mainly absorbed from the upper part of the gastrointestinal tract or are unstable in the medium of distal intestinal regions. Gastroretentive dosage forms can be floating, expandable, bioadhesive, modified shape and high density systems according to the physical property leading to prolongation of gastric residence time. (Kiss, 2005)

The development of gastro-retentive dosage forms (GRDF) will result in new and significant treatment alternatives, including

- It is especially effective in sparingly soluble and insoluble drugs. It is known that, as the solubility of a drug decreases, the time available for drug dissolution becomes less adequate and thus the transit time becomes a significant factor affecting drug absorption. To override this problem, erodible, gastroretentive dosage forms have been developed that provide continuous, controlled administration of sparingly soluble drugs at the absorption site.
- GRDFs greatly improve the pharmacotherapy of the stomach through local drug release, leading to high drug concentration at the gastric mucosa. (For e.g. Eradicating *Helicobacter pylori* from the submucosal tissue of stomach) making it possible to treat stomach and duodenal ulcers, gastritis and oesophagitis and reduce the risk of gastric carcinoma.

- GRDFs can be used as carriers for drugs with so-called absorption windows. These substances for e.g. antiviral, antifungal and antibiotic agents (sulphonamides, quinolones, penicillins, cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, tetracyclines etc.), are taken up only from very specific sites of the GI mucosa.

1.3 BASIC GIT PHYSIOLOGY

The gastrointestinal tract is a tube about 9m long that runs from the mouth to the anus and includes throat (pharynx), esophagus, stomach, small intestine and large intestine. The gastro intestinal tract is always in a state of continuous motility called as peristaltic movement. (SR., 2003) The gastrointestinal tract is categorized into three main parts; stomach, small intestine (duodenum, jejunum, and ileum) and large intestine.

- Stomach: The fundus and the body help in storage of food whereas pylorus is for mixing and grinding process. The fundus exerts a steady pressure on the gastric contents, pressing them towards the distal stomach to pass the contents through the pyloric valve into the small intestine. For this purpose, particle should be of the order of 1-2mm. Mucus and gastric acid are secreted in the stomach by specialized cell in stomach lining. Mucus is secreted by goblet cells and gastric acid by parietal cells. Under fasting conditions the stomach is a collapsed bag with a residual volume of 50ml and contains a small amount of gastric fluid (pH 1-3) and air. (CB., 2012)

Fig 1. 3 Anatomy of stomach

- b. Small intestine: The small intestine is the part of the gastrointestinal tract followed by the stomach and is composed of duodenum, jejunum and ileum. Among the GIT organs, much of the digestion and absorption of food takes place in this part.
- c. Large intestine: The large intestine is the thick, lower end of the digestive system consisting of appendix, colon and rectum. Its function is to absorb body water from the matter and to pass waste material from the body.

1.4 FACTORS AFFECTING GASTRIC RESIDENCE TIME OF FDDS

The gastric retention time (GRT) of dosage form is controlled by several factors that affect their efficacy as a gastroretentive system.

1.4.1 Physiological factors

- a. Size of the tablet: Retention of floating dosage forms in stomach depends on the size of tablet. Dosage forms having diameter greater than the diameter of the pyloric sphincter escape from the gastric emptying and remain within the gastric region. Small tablets are emptied from the stomach during the digestive phase, but large ones are expelled during the house keeping waves. (Verma, 2013)
- b. Density of tablet: Density is the main factor affecting the gastric residence time of dosage form. A buoyant dosage form having a density less than that of the gastric fluids floats, since it is away from the pyloric sphincter, the dosage unit is retained in the stomach for a prolonged period. A density of less than 1.0g/ml i.e. less than that of gastric contents has been reported. (Verma, 2013)
- c. Shape of tablet: The shape of dosage form is one of the factors that affect its gastric residence time. Six shapes (ring tetrahedron, cloverleaf, string, pellet, and disk) were screened In-Vivo for their gastric retention potential. The tetrahedron (each leg 2cm long) rings (3.6 cm in diameter) exhibited nearly 100% retention at 24h. (Anupama Sarawade, 2014)
- d. Viscosity grade of polymer: Drug release and floating properties of FDDS are greatly affected by viscosity of polymers and their interaction. Low viscosity polymers (e.g., HPMC K100 LV) were found to be more beneficial than high viscosity polymers (e.g., HPMC K4M) in improving floating properties. In addition, a decrease in the

release rate was observed with an increase in polymer viscosity. (Ching Mien Oh, 2015)

1.4.2 Biological factors

- a. Gender: Women have slower gastric emptying time than do men. Mean ambulatory GRT in meals (3.4 ± 0.4 hours) is less compared with their age and race-matched female counterparts (4.6 ± 1.2 hours), regardless of the weight, height and body surface.
- b. Age: Low gastric emptying time is observed in elderly than that in younger subjects. Intrasubject and intersubject variations are also observed in gastric and intestinal transit time. Elderly people, especially those over 70 years have a significantly longer GRT.
- c. Posture
 - i. Upright position: An upright position protects floating forms against postprandial emptying because the floating form remains above the gastric contents irrespective of its size.
 - ii. Supine position: This position offers no reliable protection against early and erratic emptying. In supine subjects large dosage forms (both conventional and floating) experience prolonged retention. The gastric retention of floating forms appear to remain buoyant anywhere between the lesser and greater curvature of the stomach. On moving distally, these units may be swept away by the peristaltic movements that propel the gastric contents towards the pylorus, leading to significant reduction in GRT compared with upright subjects.
- d. Concomitant intake of drugs: Drugs such as prokinetic agents (e.g., metoclopramide and cisapride), anti cholinergics (e.g., atropine or propantheline), opiates (e.g., codeine) may affect the performance of FDDS. The co-administration of GI-motility decreasing drugs can increase gastric emptying time. (Anupama Sarawade, 2014)

1.5 APPROACHES FOR INCREASING GASTROINTESTINAL RESIDENCE TIME

Various approaches have been used to increase gastrointestinal residential time. These include:

1.5.1 High density system

The density of gastric content is approximately similar to that of water. When the density of dosage form is higher than that of gastric fluid, the dosage form sinks at the bottom of the stomach. The sinked dosage form does not get emptied from stomach as it can withstand peristaltic contractions. (Bhardwaj L, 2011)

The only major drawback with these systems is that it is technically difficult to manufacture them with a large amount of drug (>50%) and achieve required density of 2.4-2.8g/cm³. Diluent such as barium sulphate (density=4.9), zinc oxide, titanium oxide and iron powder must be used to manufacture such high density formulation. (Swapnil Lembhe, 2016)

1.5.2 Bio adhesive / Mucoadhesive drug delivery system

Mucoadhesive system adhere to the gastric mucosa and increase the residence time by increasing the duration of contact between dosage form and biological membrane, thereby improving the bioavailability. This approach involves the use of bio adhesive polymers, which can adhere to the epithelial surface in the stomach. Materials such as Carbopol, chitosan, polycarbophil, lectins, PEG, HPMC, tragacanth imparts mucoadhesive property. However, it is difficult to maintain adhesivity of system to the mucosal lining due to rapid turnover rate of gastric mucus. (Bithi, 2018)

1.5.3 Swelling and expanding system

The swelling and expanding system that are also called “Plug type system” exhibit a tendency to get logged in the pyloric sphincters. The expandable system is incorporated with a compressed system, which expands on contact with gastric fluid. The expansion leads to increment in size beyond the size of sphincter. This results in retention of the dosage form in the stomach for a long period of time.

Sustained and controlled release required proper selection of polymer; that is the polymer with the right weight and swelling properties. The polymer swelling occurs when fluid is imbibed from the surrounding into the spaces of the cross-linking of the polymer chains and matrices. These cross links also maintain the structural integrity of the polymer matrix and prevents polymer dissolution. The more the cross-linking, the longer polymer integrity is maintained but leads to reduced swelling ability of the polymer and vice versa. (Santosh Shep, 2011)

Fig 1. 5 .3 Swelling and expanding system

1.5.4 Magnetic drug delivery system

This system involves the incorporation of small magnet in the core or matrix of the system and application of another magnet on the abdomen over the position of stomach externally. However, there is the problem of placing the magnet externally at right position with precision. (PL, 2006)

Fig 1. 5 .4 GRDDS base on application of magnetic force

1.5.5 Raft forming system

The basic mechanism involved in the raft formation includes the formation of viscous cohesive gel in the contact with gastric fluids, wherein each portion of the liquid swells forming a continuous layer called a raft. The raft floats because of the buoyancy created by the formation of CO₂ and act as a barrier to prevent the reflux of gastric contents like HCl and enzymes into the esophagus. Usually, the system contains a gel forming agent and alkaline bicarbonates or carbonates responsible for the formation of to make the system less dense and float on the gastric fluids. (Bithi, 2018)

1.5.6 Floating drug delivery system

Floating Drug Delivery System (FDDS) is the part of gastric drug delivery system that floats/buoyant on the surface of the gastric fluids due to their low density for prolonged period of time without affecting gastric emptying rate. While the system is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is slowly released at a desired rate from the floating system and after the complete release; the residual system is expelled from the stomach. This leads to increase in the GRT and better control over fluctuations in plasma drug concentrations. Low density delivery system provides the immediate floating on the gastric content due to air entrapment within the system or due to incorporation with low density excipients. But high density delivery system initially settles down in the stomach. However, the system tends to float with the decrease in the density of the system. But such system has possibility of gastric emptying of system before the floating starts. (Rhodes, 1996)

Based on the mechanism of buoyancy, two distinctly different technologies have been utilized in development of FDDS that are: effervescent and non-effervescent systems.

- a. Effervescent system: This approach provides based on formation of carbon dioxide (CO_2) gas. It utilizes effervescent components such as sodium bicarbonate or sodium carbonate and additionally citric or tartaric acid that generates gas when in contact with the gastrointestinal fluids, CO_2 is released and gets entrapped in swollen hydrocolloids, which provides buoyancy to the dosage forms. (Swapnil Lembhe, 2016)

Fig 1. 5. 6 Effervescent System

- b. Non-effervescent system: Based on the mechanism of swelling of the polymer or bio adhesion to the mucosal layer of gastrointestinal tract, non-effervescent system is developed. This system includes the use of gel forming or highly swelling agents (HPMC), matrix forming materials (e.g. polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polystyrene) as well as bio adhesive polymer (e.g. chitosan, Carbopol). (Swapnil Lembhe, 2016)

1.6 DRUG RELEASE KINETICS

An appropriate drug release test is required to characterize the drug product and ensure batch to batch reproducibility and consistent pharmacological/biological activity and to evaluate scale up and post approval changes such as manufacturing site changes, component and composition changes. The release of drug from a sustained release formulation is controlled by various factors through different mechanism such as diffusion, erosion or osmosis. Several mathematical models are proposed by many researchers to describe the drug release profiles from various systems. In

order to characterize the kinetics of drug release from dosage forms several model dependent methods are reported by various researchers. The model dependent methods all rely upon a curve fitting procedure. Different mathematical functions have been used to model the observed data. Both the linear and non-linear models are being used in practice for dissolution modelling. Linear models include Zero order, Higuchi, Hixon - Crowell, Quadratic and Polynomials, whereas the nonlinear models include First order, Weibull, Kors Meyer - Peppas, Logistic etc.

There are several linear and non-linear kinetic models to describe release mechanisms and to compare test and Reference dissolution profiles are as follows:

- Zero order kinetics
- First order kinetics
- Korsmeyer-Peppas model
- Higuchi model

1.6.1 Zero order kinetics

Drug dissolution from dosage forms that do not disaggregate and release the drug slowly can be represented by the equation: (Suvakanta Dash, 2010)

$$Q_0 - Q_t = K_0 t$$

Rearrangement of above equation,

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t$$

Where,

Q_t is the amount of drug dissolved in time t ,

Q_0 is the initial amount of drug in the solution (most times, $Q_0 = 0$) and

K_0 is the zero order release constant expressed in units of concentration/time. To study the release kinetics, data obtained from in vitro drug release studies, are plotted as cumulative amount of drug released versus time.

Fig 1.6.1 Zero order drug release

1.6.2 First order release kinetics

This model is used to describe the absorption and elimination of some drugs, although it is difficult to understand the mechanism on the theoretical basis. The drug release which follows the first order kinetic can be expressed by the equation (Suvakanta Dash, 2010)

$$\text{Log } C = \text{Log } C_0 - Kt/2.303$$

Where,

C_0 = Initial concentration of drug

K = First order constant

t = time

The data obtained are plotted as log cumulative percentage drug remaining verses time, which yield a straight line with slope $=K/2.303$.

1.6.3 Higuchi model

Higuchi proposed this model in 1961 to describe the drug release from matrix system. Higuchi model is based on the hypotheses that:

- (i) initial drug concentration in the matrix is much higher than drug solubility
- (ii) drug diffusion takes place only in one dimension (edge effect must be negligible)
- (iii) drug particles are much smaller than system thickness

- (iv) matrix swelling and dissolution are negligible
- (v) drug diffusivity is constant and
- (vi) perfect sink conditions are always attained in the release environment.

Higuchi model is given by the equation:

$$Q_t = A \sqrt{D(2C - C_s) C_s t}$$

Q- the amount of drug released per time t per unit area A

C- the initial concentration of the drug

C_s- the drug solubility in the matrix media

D- drug diffusivity of the drug molecules

The above relation is valid during all the time, except when the total depletion of the drug in the therapeutic system is achieved. To study the dissolution from a planar heterogeneous matrix system, where the drug concentration in the matrix is lower than its solubility and the release occurs through pores in the matrix, the expression is given by equation:

$$Q_t = \sqrt{D \frac{\delta}{\tau} (2C - \delta C_s) C_s t}$$

D- the diffusion co-efficient of drug molecule in the solvent

δ- the porosity of the matrix

τ- the tortuosity of the matrix

Tortuosity is defined as the dimensions of radius and branching of the pores and canals in the matrix.

After simplification, Higuchi model can be written as:

$$Q_t = K H. t^{1/2}$$

where,

KH is the Higuchi dissolution constant

The data obtained were plotted as cumulative percentage drug release versus square root of time. (Suvakanta Dash, 2010)

Fig 1. 6.3 Higuchi model drug release

1.6.4 Korsmeyer Peppas Model

Korsmeyer et al (1983) derived a simple relationship which describes the release of drug from a polymeric system. To illustrate the mechanism of drug release, first 60% of drug release data was fitted in Korsmeyer-Peppas model.

$$C_t/C_\infty = k t^n$$

Where,

C_t/C_∞ = fraction of drug release at time, t^n .

k = rate constant

n=release exponent

A modified form of this equation was developed to adjust the lag time (l) in the beginning of release of drug from the pharmaceutical dosage form.

$$C(t-l)/C_{\infty} = a(t-l)^n$$

Where there is possibility of a burst effect, „b“ this equation becomes

$$Ct/C_{\infty} = at^n + b$$

In the absence of lag time or burst effect „l“ and „b“ values would be zero and only „atn“ is used. This mathematical model, also known as the „Power Law“, has been used very frequently, to describe the drug release from several different Pharmaceutical modified release dosage forms.

There are several simultaneous processes considered in this model:

- Diffusion of water into the tablet.
- Swelling of tablet as water enters.
- Formation of gel.
- Diffusion of drug and filler out of the tablet.
- Dissolution of the polymer matrix.

Following assumptions were made in this model:

- The generic equation is applicable to small values of „t“ or short terms and the portion of release curve, where $Ct/C_{\infty} < 0.6$ should only use to determine the exponent ‘n’.
- Drug release in a one dimensional way.
- The ratio of system length to thickness should be at least.
- Plot made by log cumulative percentage drug release verses log time. (Suvakanta Dash, 2010)

1.7 RATIONALE FOR CLARITHROMYCIN AS A DRUG

Clarithromycin is a semi-synthetic broad spectrum macrolide antimicrobial agent used in combination for the treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and duodenal ulcer disease and for the treatment of upper and lower respiratory tract infections. Clarithromycin is absorbed rapidly from the gastrointestinal tract after oral administration. In controlled release formulation, if the concentration of antibiotic is maintained above the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), drug resistance can be reduced. Therefore, a high drug level should be the goal of the therapy. It is achieved by using a gastric floating drug delivery system, which provides optimum antibacterial activity. Short elimination half-life of clarithromycin (3-6 h), makes it a useful candidate for controlled release dosage form, and stability in an acidic environment is useful for gastro-retentive drug delivery system. (Patel, 2006)

Floating drug delivery enhances drug bioavailability by prolonging exposure to upper gastrointestinal tract absorption sites, improving drug efficacy. Floating systems have low-density systems that have sufficient buoyancy to float over the gastric contents and remain in the stomach for a prolonged period. While the system floats over the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate, which results in increased gastric retentive time and reduces the fluctuation in plasma drug concentration. (Patil M.S. & V, 2015) The controlled release of clarithromycin floating tablets reduces the likelihood of side effects than conventional tablets.

Floating tablets maintains a steady plasma concentration over an extended period which can be beneficial for providing optimum antibacterial activity. Floating tablets offer advantages in terms of ease of administration and patient compliance, reducing frequency of dosing. Floating drug delivery of clarithromycin shows sustained release there by proper duration of action at a particular site.

1.8 DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

Design of experiment is a systematic method to determine the relationship between factors affecting a process and the output of that process. In other words, it is used to find cause-and-effect relationships. This information is needed to manage process inputs to optimize the output.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

- **Kawade Prakash N, Changediya V.V.** (2021) formulated and characterized clarithromycin floating tablets using various polymers. The preformulation parameters like organoleptic properties, angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index and compatibility index of pure drug was evaluated and compiled with the pharmacopeial specifications. The study showed the optimum formulation (C7) could sustain drug release for 12 h by using ethyl cellulose in the concentration of 50 mg which increases bioavailability of the drug up to some extent to retain the dosage form on the desired site for effective period of the time. The optimized formulation followed Kors Mayer peppas release. (V.V., 2021)
- **Hardikar S, and Bhosale A,** (2018) made an attempt to formulate and evaluate gastro retentive tablets of clarithromycin prepared by using a novel polymer blend using HPMC K100LV blended with the gel isolated from the seeds of *Ocimum basilicum*. Floating tablets were prepared using clarithromycin, HPMC K100LV, and gel isolated from the seeds of *Ocimum basilicum* in various concentrations. It was observed that formulation P5 was compressed at low compression pressure (0.25ton) and released more drug up to 12h (94.4%) than the tablet formulation P6 (89.00%) prepared by applying high pressure (0.5 ton). (Hardikar S, 2018)
- **Thakur RS, Patel SS et.al.** (2022) made an attempt to formulate and evaluate FDDS containing clarithromycin for H.pylori using HPMC, clarithromycin, and different additives by wet granulation method and D-optimal design technique. The formulated tablets were evaluated for post and precompression studies and found the optimized formulation was obtained using 62.5% clarithromycin, 4.95% HPMC K15M, 18.09% HPMC K4M, 12.96% sodium bicarbonate which gave floating lag time < the 30s with a total floating time > 10h, in vitro release profile very near to the target in vitro release profile and follows anomalous diffusion as well as zero order pattern of release. (Patel S. S., 2006)
- **Saripilli R, Koralla H et.al.** (2019) made an attempt on the formulation and evaluation of gastro retentive Floating Dosage Forms of Clarithromycin using HPMC and hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC) as a release retarding polymer by wet

granulation method. The prepared tablets were evaluated for all their physicochemical properties, in vitro buoyancy, drug release, and rate order kinetics. From the results, FHM4 was selected as an optimized formulation based on their 12h drug release, minimal floating lag time, and maximum total floating time. The optimized formulation followed first-order kinetics with an erosion mechanism. (Rajeswari, 2019)

- **Nama M, Gonugunta CSR, Veerareddy PR (2008)** has performed formulation and evaluation of gastroretentive dosage forms of clarithromycin by using wet granulation method. All the formulations were evaluated for various parameters and were found to be within acceptable limits. The optimized formulation developed using 66.2% clarithromycin, 12% HPMC K4M polymer, 8% sodium bicarbonate gave floating lag time less than 3 min with a floating time of 12h, and an in vitro release profile near to the desired release. The mechanism release of clarithromycin from floating tablets is anomalous diffusion transport and follows zero order kinetics. In vivo radiographic studies suggest that the tablet has increased gastric residence time for the effective localized action of clarithromycin in the treatment of H.pylori mediated peptic ulcer. (Nama M, 2008)
- **Sundar WA, Purohit D et.al.** formulated and evaluated floating matrix tablets of clarithromycin using different grades of HPMC. Tablets containing API, HPMC, and different additives were prepared by wet granulation. The study shows that the tablet composition and mechanical strength have great influence on the floating properties and drug release. Incorporation of gas generating agent together with polymer improved drug release, besides optimal floating (floating lag time < 1.5 min; total floating time > 20h). The drug release was sufficiently sustained (more than 12 h). The optimal formulation was obtained using 50% clarithromycin, 14.47% HPMC K15M, 3.9% HPMC K4M, which gave floating lag time < 1.5 min with a floating time > 20 h, in vitro release profile very near to the target in vitro release profile. (Sundar WA, 2013)
- **Patil, M.S. and Vidyasagar, Gali and Patil, Vinayak** has performed evaluation, optimization, and evaluation of floating tablets of clarithromycin with HPMC K15M as a polymer and sodium bicarbonate as gas generating agent by wet

granulation method. The results of factorial design indicated that low level of HPMC K15M favors the preparation of floating controlled release of clarithromycin tablets. The tablets were evaluated for thickness, hardness, weight variation, floating lag time, total floating time, swelling index, drug content uniformity and in vitro drug release in 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2). The in vitro dissolution profiles of all the prepared clarithromycin floating drug delivery system formulation was found to extend the drug release over a period of 10 to 12 h and the drug release rate decreased with increase in polymer concentration. (Patil M.S. & V, 2015)

- **Venkatachalam Dr. K** has formulated and evaluated clarithromycin floating tablet by employing two different grades of HPMC K4M, HPMC K10M, HPMC K15M, chitosan by effervescent technique. The study suggested prepared tablets exhibited satisfactory physico-chemical characteristics and showed good in vitro buoyancy. HPMC K15M based matrix tablets showed significantly greater swelling indices compared with other batches. In vitro release mechanism was evaluated by subjecting the dissolution data to various kinetic models and the drug release was found to best fit to Korsmeyer-Peppas equation and followed by Higuchi model and zero order rate kinetics. (Venkatachalam, 2013)

3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The main aim of this research work is to formulate clarithromycin floating tablets.

General Objective

- To formulate and evaluate floating tablets of Clarithromycin.

Specific Objectives

- To formulate clarithromycin floating tablets using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC K15M) and sodium bicarbonate as the floating agent.
- To evaluate the floating time and floating lag time of the tablets in simulated gastric fluid.
- To determine the drug content of the tablets.
- To evaluate the in vitro drug release of the tablets.
- To perform stability studies on the tablets

4 MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1 STUDY DESIGN

Our study was experimental type.

4.2 STUDY AREA AND SITE

Nobel college Laboratory under department of Pharmacy; Nobel college, Sinamangal, Kathmandu

4.3 ETHICS APPROVAL

Ethics approval was taken from Nobel college Institutional Review Committee (NIRC), Sinamangal, Kathmandu with reference number 079/0801207

4.4 MATERIALS USED

4.4.1 Chemicals used

Clarithromycin was received as a gift sample from Asian Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. and Deurali Janta Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. Similarly, HPMC K15M was received as a gift sample from Florid Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. The following chemicals were used during studies:

Chemicals	Functionality
Clarithromycin	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
HPMC K15	Polymer
Ethyl Cellulose	Polymer
Sodium bicarbonate	Gas forming agent
Citric acid	Gas forming agent
Magnesium Stearate	Lubricant
Talc	Glidant
Lactose	Filler

4.4.2 Equipment used

Equipment	Manufacturer
Analytical balance	HANDK (HK)
UV Spectrophotometer	
Tablet Compression Machine	RIMEX
Friability Testing Apparatus	Biological museum AGRA-282005 (India)
Monsanto Hardness Tester	
Vernier Calliper	
Dissolution Testing Apparatus	Electronics India (EI), 1916

4.5 METHODOLOGY

4.5.1 Scanning for the determination of λ max for Clarithromycin

50 mg of Clarithromycin was weighed and dissolved in 50 ml methanol in a volumetric flask with continuous stirring, labeled as stock solution. Then, subsequently 100 ppm solution was prepared. The spectrum of the solution was run from 200-400 nm range in UV-Visible spectrophotometer and absorption maxima was determined at 265 nm.

4.5.2 Calibration curve

100 mg of clarithromycin was weighed accurately and added to a volumetric flask containing 0.2 M H₂SO₄. Then the volume was made up to 100 ml with 0.2 M H₂SO₄, which was labeled as stock solution. After that, solutions at concentration of 300 ppm, 350 ppm, 400 ppm, 450 ppm, and 500 ppm were prepared. The absorbance of all these solutions was measured at 265 nm in a UV-visible spectrophotometer and the results were plotted to obtain a calibration curve, and the R² value was determined.

4.5.3 Formulation of tablet

Floating matrix tablets containing Clarithromycin were prepared by the direct compression technique using various concentrations of polymers with sodium bicarbonate and citric acid as

gas-forming agents that provide an effervescent effect by releasing CO₂ gas, which helps in floating. API, along with all excipients in the required ratio as obtained from literature review, was mixed together in a polybag for 15 minutes. The blend was then compressed in a single rotary compression machine. The tablets were then labeled and kept in a polybag.

4.5.4 Experimental design

The resulting in total 9 experiments were used to optimize the chosen key factors that affects drug release and floating time given in Annex. The amount HPMC K15 and Ethyl Cellulose were selected as the factors under consideration.

The values for the upper and lower limit were selected based on the floating characteristics in the initial trials and error basis. The concentration of two parameters was kept at minimum concentration as found from the literature reviews. Then the concentration was increased till floating characteristics was obtained. The quantity for sodium bicarbonate, talc and magnesium stearate were fixed.

Floating lag time, floating time, cumulative percentage drug release hourly up to 24 h were used as response variable.

4.5.5 Pre compression parameters

- a. **Bulk density (B.D):** The total mass per bulk volume of powder. It was measured by pouring the weighed amount of powder (passed through standard sieve # 20) into a measuring cylinder and then the initial volume was noted. This initial volume is called the bulk volume. From this, the bulk density was calculated according to the formula mentioned below. It is expressed in g/cc and is given by

$$BD = m/V_o$$

Where, m=mass of the powder

V_o= bulk volume of the powder.

- b. **Tapped density (T.D):** It is the total mass per tapped volume of powder. The volume was measured by tapping the powder for 500 times. Again the tapping is done for 750 times and the tapped volume was noted (the difference between these two

volumes should be less than 2%). If it is more than 2%, tapping is continued for 1250 times and tapped volume is noted. (Singh, 2013) It is expressed in g/cc and is given by:

$$TD = m/V_i$$

Where,

m= mass of the powder.

V_i = tapped Volume of the powder

- c. **Hausner's ratio (H.R):** It is the measurement of frictional resistance of the drug. The ideal range should be 1.2 – 1.5, and is determined by dividing tapped density to bulk density. (Singh, 2013)

$$H.R = T.D / B.D$$

- d. **Carr's compressibility Index** The flowability of the powder material can be evaluated by comparing the Bulk density (BD) to the Tapped density (TD) of powder and the rate at which it gets packed down.(Singh, 2013) Compressibility index was calculated using the following formula;

$$C.I = 100 X (1 - 1/H.R.)$$

- e. **Flow properties (Angle of repose):** This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of powder or granules and the horizontal plane. The angle of repose of granules was determined by using funnel method. The funnel was fixed at a particular height (2.5 cm) on a burette stand. The powder sample was then passed through the funnel until it forms a heap. Further addition of granules is stopped as soon as the heap touches the tip of the funnel. A circle was drawn across it without disturbing the pile. The radius and height of the heap was then noted. The same procedure was repeated for three times and the average value is taken. (Rakhi B. Shah, 2008) The angle of repose was calculated by using following equation.

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$$

Where,

θ = Angle of repose

h = Height of the heap

r = Radius of the heap

4.5.6 Post compression parameters

- a. **Weight Variation:** It is performed to maintain the uniformity of weight of each tablet, which should be within specified range. It is performed by weighing 20 tablets at random and average weight is calculated. The individual weights are compared against the average weight.

$$\text{Weight variation} = (Iw - Aw) / Aw$$

Where, Iw = Individual weight, Aw = Average weight

- b. **Hardness:** Hardness indicates the ability of a tablet to withstand mechanical shocks while handling. The hardness of the tablets was determined using Monsanto hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm². In this test, 10 tablets were selected at random and hardness of each tablet was measured.
- c. **Thickness:** The dimensions of the tablet like thickness, length were measured using Vernier calipers. Ten tablets were selected randomly for this test and the average value was reported.
- d. **Friability:** Friability is the measure of the mechanical strength of the tablets. Pre-weighed tablets with a weight w₁ were placed in the Friability Testing apparatus, which was operated at 25 RPM for 4 minutes. The tablets were re-weighed to give w₂.

$$\text{Friability Percentage (\%)} = [w_1 - w_2] / w_1 \times 100$$

- e. **Buoyancy / Floating test:** Floating lag time and floating duration were determined by placing the tablets in a beaker containing 100ml 0.1N HCl. The time required for the tablet to rise to the surface and float was determined as floating time. The

duration of time for which the tablet remained consistently on the surface of the medium was determined as floating time.

- f. Swelling index:** The swelling behavior of the dosage unit was measured by studying its weight gain. The study was done by immersing the dosage form in 0.1N HCl at 37°C. After 2, 4, 6, and 8h, the tablets were removed from beaker and blotted with tissue paper to remove excess water and weighed on analytical balance. Swelling index was calculated by using the formula:

$$\text{Swelling index} = (\text{Wet weight of tablet} - \text{Dry weight of tablet}) / \text{Dry weight of tablet}$$

4.5.7 Drug content

Drug content was measured by powdering 10 tablets at random and weighing them. An accurate amount of the powder containing 100 mg of Clarithromycin was taken and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask containing 50 ml 0.2M H₂SO₄ where it was allowed to stand to ensure the complete solubility of the drug. The mixture was made up to volume with the same solvent. The solution was filtered, and 2 ml of this solution was diluted to 10 ml with 0.2M H₂SO₄ to prepare 200 ppm solution. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at the λ_{max} at about 265 nm.

4.5.8 In-vitro Dissolution Study

In-vitro dissolution test was conducted on USP II equipment. The stirring rate was 50 rpm, 900 ml of 0.1N HCL was used as the dissolution medium and maintained 37±0.5°C. Sample of 5 ml was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals of 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12, and 24h intervals, filtered and replaced with 5 ml of fresh dissolution medium. The collected samples were analyzed for the Clarithromycin content at 265 nm by using double beam UV Spectrophotometer. The percentage drug release was calculated by following formula:

$$\% \text{ Drug release} = (\text{Ab. Of Sample}) / \text{Slope} \times \text{Dilution factor} \times (1/1000)$$

4.5.9 Drug release kinetics

The *In-Vitro* release data were subjected to model fitting analysis to know the order and mechanism of drug release by treating the data according to zero order, first order, Higuchi release kinetic and Korsmeyer-Peppas model equation. Correlation coefficient (R^2 value) was obtained from the plots of these kinetic model for determining best fit and nature of drug release from the designed formulations. (Suvakanta Dash, 2010)

5 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1 DETERMINATION OF ABSORPTION MAXIMA

An UV-Visible spectrophotometric method was used for estimation of clarithromycin and maximum absorption was found to be 265 nm.

5.2 CALIBRATION CURVE OF CLARITHROMYCIN IN 0.2M H₂SO₄

Standard stock solution of pure drug containing 100 mg of clarithromycin / 100 ml were prepared in 0.2 M H₂SO₄. The working standard solutions were prepared by dilution of stock solution in 0.2 M H₂SO₄. The standard curve for clarithromycin was prepared in the range of 300-500 ppm at the selected wavelength of 265 nm. Their absorptivity values were used to determine the linearity. Solutions were scanned and Beer Lambert's law limit was obeyed in concentration range of 300-500 ppm.

S.N	Concentration	Absorbance
1.	300	0.261
2.	350	0.372
3.	400	0.502
4.	450	0.626
5.	500	0.754

The Correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9994. This suggests a good correlation among the measured values. The equation for the calibration was found as $y = 0.0025x - 0.489$.

5.3 PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF PREPARED POWDER BLENDS

Various properties of powder such as bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose were determined for several formulations from F1 to F9 and the results have been listed in the Annex . The angle of repose for the formulation ranged from 28.25 to 32.74 which indicated passable flow property of entire formulation powder. Carr's index of the powder ranged from 11.50 to 23.07 which shows powder blend has required flow property for compression. Hausner's ratio of the powder was found to be in the range of 1.12 to 1.21, considered to have fair flow property for the compression.

5.4 PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF CLARITHROMYCIN FLOATING TABLET

All the prepared formulations F1 to F9 were tested for physical parameters like hardness, thickness, weight variation, friability and found to be within the pharmacopeial limits. The results of the test were tabulated and listed in Annex . The drug content of all the formulations was determined and was found to be within the possible limit. This study indicated that all the prepared formulations were good. The results of the physical tests of the formulations were within the limits and comply with the standards. The thickness was found to be in the range of 7.54 to 7.57mm. Hardness varied from 5.14 to 7.9 kg/cm² . This ensures good handling characteristics. Friability was found to be 0.36% to 0.72%, indicating that the tablets are hard enough to withstand the external mechanical stress. The drug content on an average was found to be 92% to 104.39%. All these parameters were within acceptable limits. The results of the physical tests of many of the formulations were in the limits and comply with the standards.

5.5 FLOATING TIME AND FLOATING LAG TIME

The floating time for all the formulations was observed to be greater than 24 hours containing in 0.1 N HCL beaker at 37 °C. The floating lag time was calculated for all the formulations. The data for floating time and floating lag time were listed in Annex.

Sodium bicarbonate was used as a gas generating agent in order to float the tablet and citric acid used to maintain the acidic condition in dissolution medium. The sodium bicarbonate in the presence of dissolution medium (0.1N HCl). The gas generated is trapped and protected with in

the gel formed by hydration of the polymer, thus decreasing the density of the tablet below 1 gm/ml and the tablets becomes buoyant.

5.6 SWELLING INDEX

Swelling of HPMC K 15M was determined by water uptake observed for 8 hours. From the results, it was calculated that swelling index increases as the time passes because the polymer hydrates and swells and barriers are found in the outer surface.

5.7 In-Vitro Dissolution Studies

The results of In-Vitro dissolution study has been listed in Annex . The dissolution data of the formulation F1 to F9 varied from 69.02% to 99.06%. The FIP guideline for modified release states 3 points for dissolution testing. The first is the initial release that illustrates no dose dumping has occurred and corresponds to a drug dissolution amount of 20-30%. The second point aims to define the release pattern and is usually set at 50% of the total drug content. The final point of the guideline 38 aims to establish that ample drug has been released from the dosage form to ensure a quantitative drug release at more than or equal to 80%. The dissolution data of the optimized formulation adheres to the limits set by the FIP guidelines.

The initial drug limit of 26.51% is between the stated ranges, the second point is more than 50% at 60.7% that establishes a sustained drug release while the final point also adheres to the limit at more than 80%. These data signify that the optimized formulation dissolution data has correlation with the stated standard dissolution profile of the FIP guidelines.

5.8 Drug release kinetics studies

The kinetics values obtained for formulation F1 to F9 are shown in Annex. The values of In-Vitro release were attempted to fit into various mathematical models – zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix and Korsmeyers Peppas model. The drug release data were explored for the type of release mechanism followed. The best fit with the highest determination R^2 coefficient was shown by Korsmeyer model. Korsmeyer model have a good fit to all dissolution profiles of all tablets as shown by average R^2 values 0.968. Fitting the drug release in Higuchi equation gave an average correlation coefficient R^2 values of 0.912.

Similarly, for zero order kinetics, the average R^2 value was 0.849. Zero order release describes the release rate independent of drug concentration. For first order kinetics, the average R^2 value was 0.656. The formulations with a drug release of less than 80% were F1, F2, F4, F8. The average total HPMC and ethyl cellulose concentration for these formulations were 139.86mg and 117.5mg respectively. The lowest drug release was for F1 at 69.02% after 24 hours and the highest was 99.06% for F6. The total HPMC and ethyl cellulose concentration for this formulation were 65 mg and 70mg respectively. Formulations of F7, F3 and F9 also had high drug release at 98.27%, 88.20% and 87.24% respectively. These formulations had an average concentration of 73mg of HPMC and 85mg of ethyl cellulose.

These data shows that the optimum range for the polymers lies between 60-105mg. Whereas, weight more than 105 mg has high probability of total drug release of less than 80% after 24 h.

6 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, FUTURE WORKS AND LIMITATIONS

6.1 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present study was done to design and evaluate Clarithromycin Floating tablet for gastro retentive drug delivery system. Clarithromycin is a semi synthetic antibiotic, belonging to macrolide family, which is effective for bacterial infection treatment, especially for *Helicobacter pylori* infection. The concept of floating drug delivery system was used to retain the drug in stomach for a prolonged time. First of all the physical compatibility study was done through literature review which showed that Clarithromycin was found to be compatible with all excipient. In the present study the attempt was made to design GRFDDS of Clarithromycin using HPMC K15M and ethyl cellulose as polymers, Citric acid and Sodium bicarbonate as a gas generating agent. The formulations were obtained as per systematic literature review.

Sodium bicarbonate and citric acid were used for effervescent properties. Despite the floating ability of HPMC matrix, due to the time it takes for swelling and gel formation, addition of sodium bicarbonate was found essential to ensure rapid floating. Since pH of stomach is elevated under fed condition, citric acid was also incorporated in the formulation to provide sufficiently acidic medium for sodium bicarbonate to react. This will allow the system to float independent of pH of medium.

The tablets were prepared by direct compression method. The formulations were designed with the aid of literature review and all the designed 9 batches of formulations were evaluated for hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, assay, swelling index and *In-Vitro* drug release. All the prepared tablets exhibited satisfactory physico-chemical properties. The *In-Vitro* dissolution was performed using USP dissolution apparatus II (paddle) at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50 rpm in 900 ml 0.1N HCl. All the formulations remained buoyant for more than 18 h. The formulation F6 gave the maximum release which is 99.06% at 24 hour of dissolution time. The formulation F6 consist of 65mg HPMC K15M and 70 mg of ethyl cellulose. Whereas, the formulation F8 gave the minimum drug release of 66.66% at 24 hour of dissolution time. The formulation F8 consist 145mg of HPMC K 15M and 70mg of ethyl cellulose. This clearly shows that the combination of HPMC

K15M and ethyl cellulose forms the matrix system which helps to retard the drug release for extended release.

In-Vitro drug release data were fitted in different kinetics models like zero order, first order, Higuchi model and Peppas model. Majority of the designed GRFDDS of Clarithromycin displayed Korsmeyer Peppas model with average R^2 value 0.968 and remained buoyant for more than 18 hours.

This study proves GRFDDS of Clarithromycin can be designed using HPMC K15M and ethyl cellulose as matrix polymers and sodium bicarbonate for gas generating in appropriate amount. Such system can remain buoyant for more than 12 h along with the sustained drug release at the region of stomach and thus possible enhancements of medication at targeted site and reduce systemic adverse effect.

6.2 Future works

- Stability studies of the optimized formulation
- The *In-Vitro* drug release can be studied at various pH conditions, since the pH of the stomach varies in fasted and fed state.
- Pharmacokinetics studies for *In-Vitro* and *In-Vivo* correlation can be calculated.

6.3 Limitations

- Comparison with the marketed sample was not done due to the unavailability of the formulation in Nepal
- The study was done only on small batch size and thus the results may vary if they are to be done on a larger scale.
- HPLC method of analysis was not used due to unavailability of HPLC for analysis, UV method of analysis was used.

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ANNEX I: Drug Specific Review- Clarithromycin

- Drug: Clarithromycin
- IUPAC name: 6-(4-dimethylamino-3-hydroxy-6-methyl-tetrahydropyran-2-yl)oxy-14-ethyl-12,13-dihydroxy-4-(5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-4,6-dimethyl-tetrahydropyran-2-yl)oxy-7-methoxy-3,5,7,9,11,13-hexamethyl-1-oxacyclotetradecane-2,10-dione
- Structure:

Table 7-1 Clarithromycin

- Molecular formula: C₃₈H₆₉NO₁₃
- CAS No: 81103-11-9
- Molecular weight: 747.96 g/mol
- Route: Oral, IV
- Melting point: 217-220°C
- Bioavailability: 50
- Protein Binding: ~ 70% protein bound
- Half life: 3-4 hrs
- Functional category: Antibiotic

- Appearance: White to off white crystalline powder
- Solubility: Practically insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, soluble in acetone and methylene chloride
- Mechanism of action: Clarithromycin is first metabolized to 14-OH clarithromycin, which is active and works synergistically with its parent compound. It penetrates bacteria cell wall and reversibly binds to domain V of the 23S ribosomal RNA of the 50S subunit of the bacterial ribosome, blocking translocation of aminoacyl transfer-RNA and polypeptide synthesis. Clarithromycin also inhibits the hepatic microsomal CYP3A4 isoenzyme and P-glycoprotein, an energy-dependent drug efflux pump.

Pharmacokinetics:

Absorption: Clarithromycin is well-absorbed, acid stable and may be taken with food.

Distribution: Clarithromycin is diffused into most tissues and phagocytes. Due to the high concentration in phagocytes, clarithromycin is actively transported to the site of infection. The concentration of clarithromycin in the tissues can be over 10 times higher than in plasma. Highest concentrations are found in liver and lung tissue.

Metabolism: Hepatic; half-life of clarithromycin is 3-4 hour.

Excretion: 20-30 percent excreted in urine via kidneys and rest is excreted into bile.

HPMC

Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) is the most important hydrophilic carrier for the preparation of oral controlled drug delivery systems. One of its most important characteristics is the high swellability, which has a significant effect on the release kinetics of the incorporated drug. Upon contact with water or biological fluid, the latter diffuses into the devices, resulting in polymer chain relaxation with volume expansion. Then, the incorporated drug diffuses out of the system. (Siepmann and Peppas et. al, 2001)

Chemistry of HPMC

The General structure of HPMC is shown in figure 2-3. (Adapted from (Rowe, Sheskey, and Quinn 2009). It is odorless and tasteless, white or creamy-white fibrous or granular powder. (Rowe, Sheskey and Quinn 2009)

The structure of HPMC is a cellulose backbone with ether linked methoxyl and hydroxypropyl side group substituents attached through either linkages to the cellulose chain hydroxyl groups. During manufacturing, pulp cellulose is treated with caustic soda and reacted with methyl chloride and propylene oxide to create the substituted polymer, and the grades of HPMC used in the matrix tablets have substantial degrees of methoxyl but rather less hydroxypropyl substitution. It should be noted that the latter introduces a secondary hydroxyl group, although in HPMC, unlike some other cellulose ethers, there is little evidence for additive substitution of these groups.

Table 7-2: General Structure of HPMC

Polymer properties are strongly influenced by the ratio of methoxyl and hydroxypropyl substitution. The degree of substitution and position of the methoxyl and hydroxypropoxyl groups are not the same on each anhydroglucose unit. In the structure, the substituent R represents either a $-\text{CH}_3$ or $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{OH}$ group, or a hydrogen atom. (Siepmann, 2001)

Sodium Bicarbonate and Citric Acid

Sodium Bicarbonate can be used as an alkalizing agent. It is generally used in pharmaceutical formulations as a source of carbon dioxide in effervescent tablets and granules. In effervescent tablets and granules, sodium bicarbonate is usually formulated with citric and/or tartaric acid

When the tablets or granules meet with water, a chemical reaction occurs, carbon dioxide is evolved. This is used either to break in case of effervescent fast disintegrating tablets or in cases of floating drug delivery system with opposite task (Rowe, 2009)

Magnesium Stearate

This falls under the functional category of lubricants for tablets or capsules. Magnesium stearate is a very fine, light white, precipitated or milled, impalpable powder of low bulk density, having a faint odor of stearic acid and a characteristic taste. The powder is greasy to the touch and readily adheres to the skin. It may be used in the concentration of 0.25 to 5%.

ANNEX II: Final Formulation Composition of Clarithromycin Floating Tablets

Formulation	Drug	HPMC K15M	Ethyl Cellulose	Citric acid	Sodium bicarbonate	Talc	Mag. Sterate	Filler
F1	250	162	105	10	20	2	4	48
F2	250	145	140	10	10	2	4	39
F3	250	105	140	10	20	2	4	69
F4	250	105	155	10	20	2	4	55
F5	250	105	105	10	20	2	4	104
F6	250	65	70	10	20	2	4	179
F7	250	49	105	10	20	2	4	161
F8	250	145	70	10	20	2	4	99
F9	250	65	140	10	20	2	4	109

All quantities are in mg, the weights given are for each tablet.

ANNEX III: Pre- Compression properties of Clarithromycin powder

Formulation	Angle of repose (in degrees)	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's ratio
F1	30.87	0.53	0.625	14.52	1.17
F2	32.21	0.485	0.576	15.25	1.18
F3	28.79	0.44	0.5	11.50	1.13
F4	27.33	0.45	0.506	10.71	1.12
F5	32.74	0.410	0.533	23.07	1.3
F6	31.41	0.54	0.625	13.04	1.15
F7	28.25	0.52	0.6	13.04	1.15
F8	29.22	0.55	0.652	15.96	1.19
F9	30.46	0.49	0.592	17.35 _{sss}	1.21

ANNEX IV: Post- Compression properties of Clarithromycin Floating Tablet

Formulation	Hardness (g/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
F1	5.35	6.43	0.43	98
F2	5.50	6.39	0.36	94
F3	5.90	6.04	0.51	99.83
F4	6.50	5.88	0.36	92.67
F5	5.41	6.32	0.56	98
F6	7.9	5.36	0.54	94.33
F7	7.83	5.64	0.49	96.14
F8	5.28	6.37	0.67	99.33
F9	5.14	6.54	0.72	98.67

ANNEX V: Buoyancy of Formulated Clarithromycin Floating Tablet

Formulation	Floating lag time (Sec)	Total Floating Time(hr)
F1	5	24
F2	6	24
F3	9	24
F4	420	24
F5	40	24
F6	14	24
F7	210	24
F8	5	24
F9	120	24

ANNEX VI: Swelling Index

Formulation	Swelling index(2hr)	Swelling Index(8hr)
F1	1.07	1.76
F2	1.00	2.08
F3	1.12	1.66
F4	1.07	1.7
F5	1.12	1.81
F6	1.22	2.62
F7	1.25	2.6
F8	1.20	2.37
F9	1.10	1.856

ANNEX VII: Dissolution Profile of Clarithromycin Floating Tablet

Time (hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	2.81	2.48	2.31	2.7	2.48	2.48	2.64	1.97	1.69
2	5.91	5.46	5.51	5.6	5.51	5.85	5.63	4.95	4.44
3	9.28	8.66	8.94	8.9	8.89	9.90	9.28	8.33	8.83
4	12.94	12.21	13.16	12.9	12.83	14.51	14.18	12.21	13.56
5	16.71	15.98	17.66	17.4	17.10	19.86	20.36	16.43	18.68
6	21.09	22.05	23.57	23.1	22.73	25.93	27.51	21.15	24.75
7	26.33	28.24	30.38	29.5	29.03	33.24	35.10	26.21	31.84
8	32.51	34.54	38.53	36.2	36.23	42.02	43.37	31.44	38.76
9	39.15	40.95	46.91	43.1	43.71	51.69	52.65	37.24	46.13
10	45.96	48.32	56.08	50.9	51.92	62.66	62.61	43.65	54.34
11	53.21	56.25	66.09	59.3	60.81	74.31	73.58	51.02	64.46
12	60.98	64.46	76.89	68.3	70.37	86.63	85.89	58.67	75.26
24	69.02	72.96	88.20	77.9	81.06	99.06	98.27	66.66	87.24

ANNEX VIII: Regression Coefficient (R^2) values of formulated Clarithromycin Floating Tablet

Formulations	Zero order	First Order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer
	R^2			
F1	0.8444	0.6668	0.9134	0.9696
F2	0.8418	0.6586	0.9111	0.9672
F3	0.8514	0.6623	0.9073	0.9689
F4	0.8473	0.6637	0.9134	0.9678
F5	0.8534	0.6656	0.9124	0.9694
F6	0.8509	0.6625	0.9043	0.9692
F7	0.8509	0.6591	0.9103	0.9666
F8	0.8481	0.6384	0.9209	0.9691
F9	0.8598	0.6307	0.9207	0.9677

ANNEX IX: Graph of Drug Release Kinetics model

Higuchi release F1-F4

Higuchi release F5-F9

